

1972

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
sixteenth annual report

Acknowledgements

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for the year ending June 30, 1972

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¹ Until his death, June 15, 1972

² Dr. Baker succeeded Mr. Vosper November 13, 1971

³ Replaced Committee on the Laboratory November 13, 1971

⁴ Mr. Grove died in December 1971. Mr. Breedin joined the staff June 1, 1972.

introduction

the year 1971-72

If there is a common thread woven through the Council's activities during 1971-72, it is the effective and economical management of libraries. It should not be assumed, however, that because the Council has been significantly interested in technology and improvement of methods, this is our primary and ultimate concern. Efficiency and economical operation are only the means to an end, to our hoped-for goal of helping libraries in this country and elsewhere shift more effectively from a pressing concentration upon their own internal problems to their proper purpose of promoting scholarship and inculcating learning. For if humanists and scientists of all disciplines are to make important and needed contributions to society, they must continue to have adequate access to the world's literature and knowledge, and in this libraries must play the key role. Only if the operations of libraries are as good as they can be will it be possible for them to make a much greater investment of funds and talents in direct help to scholarship and learning in the future.

We often hear dire predictions of the displacement of personnel by automation and other technology. This should not be allowed to happen, for there are not nearly enough professional librarians in most of our libraries. It is probably true that there will be a change in the responsibilities of some librarians as more and more routine duties are performed by machines. It is also true that in this change librarians will discover new opportunities for service as they attempt to meet the growing need for more direct work with students and scholars and for research and development activities in the libraries themselves.

We shall continue as best we can to serve the interest of libraries, and we shall continue to urge others who are in a position to do so to help.

FRED C. COLE
President

the academic library

Of the four grants the Council on Library Resources made in its first fiscal year (1956-57), two went to universities – to Rutgers University for a two-year study entitled “Target for Research in Library Work” and to the University of Virginia to consider “Closed Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation.”¹ The Council’s concern for the academic library has since been demonstrated repeatedly, and was reiterated in this, its sixteenth year, through seven new grants totalling over \$500,000. Nine previously funded projects affecting the academic library continued in various stages of operation. Major areas covered by the Council’s academic grants are:

- Management and planning.
- Computer networks and cooperative ventures (represented by seven projects discussed in section on National Library Services).
- Role of the library in the education of the undergraduate.

It is interesting to note that three June 1972 publications of the Carnegie Commission on Higher Education in its “Reports and Recommendations” series suggest that the Council’s focus has not been misdirected. In *The More Effective Use of Resources: An Imperative for Higher Education*, the Commission calls for more institutional research and notes a variety of ways for colleges and universities to cut expenditures in the years ahead through more effective use of their resources.² In its *Fourth Revolution: Instructional Technology in Higher Education*, the Commission devotes a chapter to “Libraries and the Information Revolution,” in which it recommends as a first priority “the introduction of new technologies to help libraries continue to improve their services to increasing numbers of users.”³ And in *Reform on Campus: Changing Academic Programs*, the Commission looks at “The Library as a Learning Center” and proposes that it “should become a more active participant in the instructional process with an added proportion of funds, perhaps as much as a doubling.”⁴

¹ II:24; IV:22-23. Citations in this form refer to the Council’s annual reports: for example to the *2nd Annual Report*, page 24.

² Carnegie Commission on Higher Education, *The More Effective Use of Resources* (New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1972).

³ Carnegie Commission on Higher Education, *Fourth Revolution* (New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1972).

⁴ Carnegie Commission on Higher Education, *Reform on Campus* (New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1972).

The Council has committed to the programs to be described in this section nearly two million dollars. It has also encouraged other granting institutions to provide an additional three-quarters of a million dollars for these same programs. Without the Council's active intervention, these additional funds might not have been made available to library projects.

MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING

The Council has consistently ranked the effective use of academic library resources high on its priority list. With the National Center for Educational Statistics projecting annual college and university library expenditures totalling \$1 billion by 1974-75, the need for improved management and planning in the nation's academic libraries becomes clearer than ever.⁵ Two Council-supported studies—"Organization and Staffing of the Libraries of Columbia University" by Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc., and "On the Economics of Library Operations in Colleges and Universities" by Mathematica, Inc. — were completed in 1972 and are expected to be published in the 1972-73 fiscal year.

Long range planning

The Mathematica study is believed by its authors to be "as complete and thorough an analysis as possible of the available economic data on college and university libraries." Counseling on the need for long-range planning, the report suggests that in the next few decades "profound modification in the manner in which libraries are run may virtually be inevitable." In conclusion, the report reads: "It becomes essential to begin planning for the changeover in a systematic manner, rather than leaving the shape of the new arrangements to haphazard developments."⁶

Library planning office

The Booz, Allen & Hamilton study is the second done for the Council in the past three years and, like the first, "Problems in University Library Management" (1970), it has resulted in immediate follow-up action:⁷

- As an outgrowth of the first study, an Office of University Library Management Studies within the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) was set up with a \$130,000 Council grant in 1970;

⁵ National Center for Educational Statistics, *Projections of Educational Statistics to 1980-81*, 1971 Edition (Washington: Government Printing Office, 1972). On page 92 it is forecast that Educational and General (E&G) expenditures for U. S. colleges and universities in 1974-75 will be \$24.6 billion (in 1970-71 dollars). With higher education library costs traditionally averaging 4.2 percent of E&G expenditures, the academic library will spend \$1.03 billion in 1974-75.

⁶ XV:12.

⁷ XV:11-12.

- As a result of the second, a Columbia University Libraries Planning Office has been created and funded for a three-year period with a \$126,308 Council grant.

The 1971 Booz, Allen & Hamilton report and the library planning office it helped to initiate will be useful far beyond the confines of the Columbia University Libraries – the report, as a carefully documented case history of a management study in a large university library; the planning office, because its undertakings (unsuccessful as well as successful) can serve as a model from which others may profit.

**ARL
management
office**

The Council-supported ARL Office of University Library Management Studies, now in its second year, has already demonstrated its significance in working toward solutions to the management problems that face most major academic libraries. Since its focus is on a broad spectrum of institutions, it necessarily approaches the task in a more generalized manner than will the Columbia unit. With the help of an ARL advisory committee, the office has developed some important tools for library directors to use as they attempt to deal effectively with various aspects of management. One of them, in the test phase now, is a manual: "Library Management Review and Analysis Program: A Handbook for Guiding Change and Improvement in Research Library Management." The office also carries on a wide correspondence and information exchange with library management programs and people in this and other countries. In addition, the director spends a good part of his time at ARL member libraries, acting sometimes as consultant and sometimes as leader or participant in management workshops. He has in these capacities been involved in the two CLR-funded management activities below.

**Joint
University
Libraries
R & D unit**

Because the academic library holds a unique position in its parent institution as far as its functions, facilities, and purpose are concerned, it has long been felt that there is much to be gained by establishing within an active library a model research and development unit. Thus library problems and plans can be dealt with in the library framework by a staff of library-oriented people. It was for this reason that the Council in 1969 and again in 1971 provided funds to establish and operate such a unit in the Joint University Libraries (JUL) serving Vanderbilt University and Scarritt and George Peabody Colleges in Nashville, Tennessee.⁸

During the year the unit continued work on such projects as preparation of personnel policies and administrative procedures, acquisitions statistics gathering, modification of the JUL accounting and

⁸ XIV:13.

management information systems, and program budgeting concepts. The unit anticipates adding to its staff in the very near future a systems specialist who will conduct a complete systems study for the JUL, thus adding another dimension to the unit's work.

**Library
staff
development**

Another kind of approach to effective management is being made in a training program now in progress at the Cornell University Libraries. Guided by the Center for Planning and Development of the American Management Association, this twelve-month effort at staff development will include five-day retreats and seminars, library visits by consultants, planning sessions, and the like. Upon completion of the project the Cornell University Libraries staff should not only have a clearer idea of both short- and long-term objectives and strategies but should also have acquired the necessary skills for continued effective planning.

**In other
action**

In other action expected to assist the academic policy maker, the Council made a grant in 1971-72 to the Association of American Colleges for support of a small invitational conference on library policy, and to the University of Colorado to aid in the publication of Ralph Ellsworth's *Academic Library Buildings: A Guide to Architectural Issues and Solutions*, which was prepared with assistance also from Educational Facilities Laboratories.

THE LIBRARY IN UNDERGRADUATE EDUCATION

While the successful management and effective resource sharing of major academic libraries benefit the entire campus community, these are of marginal value to the undergraduate who has not learned how to relate fully his course work to his college's library. The Council's awareness of this situation resulted in the College Library Program, which it initiated in 1969 through matching grants to the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) for the support of projects designed to bring the college library into a central position in the educational process.⁹ In the three years since, nine colleges and universities have invested a total of \$540,000 of their own funds, over and above normal library budgets, to match a similar amount from the joint CLR-NEH program.

A key factor in all nine projects is expanded communication between major library users (students and faculty) and library personnel. One recipient's observation on reasons for the "lack of collaboration" between library and users explains in part the Council's decision to initiate the program: "It does not result from lack of interest on the part

⁹ XV:34-35.

of faculty and library staff. Nor is it due to absence of communication between the two groups. This condition seems to exist in many instances because no time is provided for adequate planning that includes both groups."

**N.C. Central
emphasizes
cooperation**

During the year covered by this report, three institutions of higher learning received matching grants for programs that were submitted with the full cooperation and endorsement of administration and faculty. North Carolina Central University, in Durham, predicates its project on the belief that optimum use of library facilities depends upon effective cooperation between library staff and teaching faculty. An initial two-month period will bring faculty and library staff together for evaluation of present facilities used in instruction in the humanities. Later meetings will be structured to help both groups become more aware of the other's needs and expectations, as well as those of the student body. As the program advances library staff members will serve on planning-teaching teams. An important aspect of the project is the use of graduate assistants from the University's School of Library Science, who will work with undergraduates to help them find and interpret library resources.

**Swarthmore
divisional
librarian**

Swarthmore College's program is based on a major self-study of both curriculum and library operations conducted by the Pennsylvania college in 1966-67. The recommendations, which were subsequently adopted by the faculty, included one for the creation of "divisional librarian" positions in each of the three divisions of the College curriculum in order to provide support for the College's expanded independent study program. Swarthmore begins its implementation of this recommendation by the employment of a divisional librarian of the humanities, who will assist students in research for courses and independent study projects, and faculty members in the bibliographical aspects of teaching. It is the College's hope that this will bring the library one step closer to achieving the role of "teaching library."

**Howard's
dual-purpose
program**

Howard University in Washington, D. C. has taken a different approach by attempting to establish the library as an integral part of the total life of the University. This will be done by demonstrating the library's ability not only to respond to students' curricular needs and interests but also to stimulate and anticipate other intellectual requirements in a broad range of areas. One aspect of the five-year program will be a student information/orientation service which, through a variety of media and methods and on as personalized a basis as possible, will make undergraduate students aware that the library can serve both classroom and noncurricular needs. A second element of the

project is a series of workshops which will demonstrate the library's capabilities as an active agent of ideas and thought.

Core collection activity

The American Library Association's (ALA) core collection project, which will result in a 40,000-title book catalog produced from machine-readable records, is moving ahead although more slowly than expected when the Council made the grant in 1969.¹⁰ It now appears that the editorial work on the entries will be completed in 1973, with publication and distribution by ALA to follow immediately thereafter.

A summary of Council-supported academic library projects active in 1971-72 follows: (The first column shows grants approved in 1971-72; the second, payments on new grants and on grants approved in earlier years. The original amounts and dates of earlier grants that were not fully paid at the beginning of fiscal 1972 are given in brackets [] at the end of each entry.

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for development from machine-readable records, to be published in book form, of an approximately 40,000-title core collection catalog that will constitute an acceptable minimum for the support of the average college instructional program of good quality. [\$290,502 – 1969]	—————	\$ 65,072
Association of American Colleges , toward support of a small invitational conference to explore library policy decision making.	\$ 2,160	375
Association of Research Libraries (ARL) , toward establishment of an office of university library management studies within ARL to further the work initiated by the Council-sponsored Booz, Allen, & Hamilton management study. [\$130,000 – 1971]	—————	60,000
Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc. , to conduct a study of the Columbia University library organization and staffing. [\$90,000 – 1971]	—————	39,782
Columbia University , three-year support for establishment of a planning office within the University Libraries. This office will participate in university-wide planning efforts, coordinate library planning, formulate budgets, participate in regional and national planning efforts, prepare reports, and make grant applications.	126,308	10,000
Consortium of Upper Middle Atlantic University Libraries , to assist member librarians to prepare and publish a guide to their resources. The guide was circulated for the first time near the end of June. [\$2,200 – 1968]	—————	1,758

¹⁰ XV:35.

Cornell University Libraries , to conduct a pioneering effort in developing a long-range plan and a planning method for the Cornell library system.	23,930	5,000
Mathematica, Inc. , for a study of the economics of university library operations. [\$25,000—1970; \$17,500—1971]	—————	6,000
Michigan State University , for publication of a directory of university extension library services at National University Extension Association (NUEA) and National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges (NASULGC) member institutions.	1,602	—————
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , to inaugurate and continue the joint College Library Program requiring matching funds from recipients. Purpose: to bring the college library further into the educational process. [\$250,000—1969; \$200,000—1970]	—————	—————
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , an additional grant of \$250,000 for the joint College Library Program of the Council and NEH.	250,000	250,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds for a Council-NEH grant of \$15,000 to State University of New York at Stony Brook in support of a faculty-student development team in history. The project will be completed in August. [\$7,500—1970]	—————	—————
North Carolina State Board of Higher Education , to study the feasibility of a central research library facility providing state-wide service. [\$10,000—1969]	—————	[\$2,066]
Ohio State University Research Foundation , to support an evaluation seminar on the Ohio State University Libraries' on-line automated system. [\$1,534—1971]	—————	1,423
University of Colorado , to assist in the publication of <i>Academic Library Buildings: A Guide to Architectural Issues and Solutions</i> by Ralph Ellsworth. This timely treatise is scheduled for publication in the fiscal year, 1972-73. The grant made it possible for the book to be made available to the public at a cost of under \$10 per copy.	10,000	10,000
Vanderbilt University , in behalf of the Joint University Libraries of Nashville (Vanderbilt, George Peabody, and Scarritt), to establish a model research and development unit. [\$171,107—1969]	—————	28,086
Vanderbilt University , to supplement funding of the Joint University Libraries' model R&D unit in Nashville, Tennessee.	89,475	—————
Wabash College , to increase the effectiveness of the College library by changing its concept from that of a storehouse of information to that of a workshop of the liberal arts. [\$50,000—1970]	—————	7,500
ACADEMIC LIBRARY TOTALS, 1971-72	\$503,475	\$482,930

national library services

It has been obvious for years that the high cost of library automation demands that in all but a few large libraries networks and consortia be formed, both to avoid duplication in effort and expenditures and to share scarce know-how and resources. As these regional groups have developed, the Council has attempted to gauge their impact on library operations, to influence their development in a way which will minimize unfavorable effects, and to advise librarians as to what to expect.

This role devolves upon the Council principally because no existing governmental agency has assumed the responsibility. While it is conceivable that the new National Commission on Libraries and Information Science may ultimately provide such guidance, the enlarged needs of libraries ideally suggest the creation of a national bibliographic center with authority to devise a national bibliographic data base in machine-readable form, to monitor software development, and to ensure that the regional systems evolving to use such services are compatible both with each other and the national libraries. In the present absence of official national guidance, the Council will continue its efforts in encouraging compatibility and standardization among regional centers moving toward automation.

**Ohio
College
Library
Center**

The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), a promising computerized regional library system which received a small Council grant in 1970, has been given an additional \$75,000 to expand its cataloging operations.¹¹ The U. S. Office of Education has also made a substantial grant for the same purpose. Although by no means perfected, OCLC's relatively successful on-line cataloging service to its approximately 50 member libraries in Ohio (plus the University of Pittsburgh and the Atlanta Cooperative College Library Center) has aroused the interest of hard-pressed librarians throughout the country, resulting in many requests for assistance in replicating the system. The operational shared cataloging function is only the first phase of the planned total service. Complete plans call for modules in the areas of serials control, technical processing, remote catalog access and circulation control, and bibliographic information and subject access retrieval. It has been estimated by OCLC officials that \$400,000 a year can now be saved by the member libraries in cataloging costs if appropriate personnel shifts or reductions are made.

**New England
Library
Information
Network**

The New England Library Information Network (NELINET) was initiated with Council support through its parent, the New England Board of Higher Education, in 1966. Additional grants were made in 1967, 1968, and 1969.¹² Originally comprising the six New England state university libraries, NELINET has a present membership of 21 libraries and three affiliates, and the capability of serving at least 64 libraries. Under a new grant from the Council, NELINET is testing the transferability of the OCLC computer-based bibliographic system to other groups of libraries. The results of this test should be most useful to others interested in replicating the OCLC system. The Baker Library at Dartmouth, one of several new NELINET members recruited under a program encouraged by the Council, serves as the evaluation-demonstration point in the NELINET-OCLC test.

**Bibliographic
automation
at Stanford**

BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-Sharing System) is an on-line bibliographic service network at Stanford University. Since its inception in 1967 it has successfully progressed through several stages with support from the U. S. Office of Education and the University itself. A recent grant of \$650,000 — \$325,000 from the Council and a similar amount from the National Endowment for the Humanities — will assist in bringing the system to operational status. This will enable the libraries to use machine-readable and machine-maintained files for purchasing and cataloging ma-

¹¹ XV:28.

¹² XV:28-29.

materials, for updating and retrieving bibliographic records, for circulation control, and for on-line bibliographic searches.

**Chicago's
five-year
plan**

Another major computer project in an academic library is the University of Chicago's program directed toward a system to handle files of up to a million records.¹³ In 1970 the project received grants of \$400,000 each from the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities. Earlier work had been supported by the National Science Foundation. Although the work proceeds more or less as anticipated, problems prevalent in selecting the right computer hardware and in designing the appropriate software continue to exist, accentuating the still-to-be-traveled distance such ambitious projects face before their goals can be achieved. Two major functions of the Chicago program are: (1) to organize, index, and store incoming data about books and (2) to identify, retrieve, and selectively display information for library users in their searches for books and other library resources.

**NAS study
published**

In late 1969 the Council commissioned a study by the Information Systems Panel of the National Academy of Sciences' (NAS) Computer Science and Engineering Board, in order to determine the present state of computer and system technologies as they relate to libraries and information systems.¹⁴ The panel undertook also to identify the roadblocks to more effective and rapid employment of these technologies for information handling, and to focus national-level attention on appropriate actions to correct identified deficiencies.

The report, *Libraries and Information Technology – A National System Challenge*, was published in early 1972.¹⁵ It lists among its conclusions this paragraph: "The primary bar to development of national computer-based library and information systems is no longer basically a technology-feasibility problem. Rather it is the combination of complex institutional and organizational human-related problems and the inadequate economic/value system associated with these activities. National leadership to solve these problems has not emerged."

The publication also contains many other important observations which merit the thoughtful consideration of the computer/systems specialists as well as of those more directly concerned with libraries.

**Intrex
in pilot
situation**

One of the significant computer projects NAS investigators studied was Intrex (Information Transfer Experiments) at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Intrex aims at developing the prototype of the

¹³ XV:27-28.

¹⁴ XIV:26.

¹⁵ Information Systems Panel of Computer Science and Engineering Board, *Libraries and Information Technology* (Washington: National Academy of Sciences, 1972).

engineering and scientific library of the future. The Council's considerable investment in the project has enabled it to move from the planning and research stage into a pilot situation.¹⁶ The project director hopes "to utilize our research findings in a prototype operational system, regional in character, centered in M.I.T. Its basic purpose will be to organize community involvement with new forms of library operations, and to establish the economic viability of such operations in the university environment." If the hope becomes an eventuality, such a system might well serve as a node in a regional network of research libraries.

**Model
Engineering
Library**

The Model Engineering Library at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology is a component of Project Intrex.¹⁷ One of its activities has been the development of the highly successful "Library Pathfinders"—single sheet guides to published information in specific subject areas. These will soon be published and distributed commercially, thus greatly enlarging the body of users and resultant benefits to them, as well as bringing in additional funds to the Model Library. Under a new Council grant of \$71,000 the unit will advance other existing projects such as development of audiovisual programs to instruct library users in a variety of reference sources and the testing of user acceptability of microfiche. The Model Engineering Library will also engage in new programs designed to make the most effective use of developing technology.

**National
Serials
Data
Program**

The Association of Research Libraries completed its two-year National Serials Data pilot project in 1972 and published its final report, *Toward a National Serials Data Program*.¹⁸ This brought to an end phase two of the program, a joint effort of the three national libraries (Library of Congress, National Agricultural Library, National Library of Medicine), with some financial and staff assistance from the Council. As fiscal year 1971-72 drew to a close, the Council prepared again to make funds and staff available for partial support of the next step in the development of a national serials data base.¹⁹ Goals for phase three include:

- An authoritative automated bibliographic resource upon which serials processing systems can be built;
- A base record of serial titles to which the International Standard Serial Number can be permanently affixed;

¹⁶ XV:26-27.

¹⁷ XIV:15-16.

¹⁸ Donald W. Johnson, *Toward a National Serials Data Program* (Washington: The Association of Research Libraries, 1972).

¹⁹ XV:20-21.

- A machine-readable bibliographic resource for serials which will supply important cataloging information to libraries and at the same time permit the uniform transfer of data on serials among libraries;
- The setting up of a base from which several kinds of library tools can be developed;
- A serial system which will constitute the U. S. segment of the developing International Serials Data System.

Cataloging in Publication

In the Council's 16-year history, grants of almost \$2 million have been awarded to the Library of Congress to bring about changes of benefit to the entire library world. Much has already been written about the development of machine-readable cataloging (MARC) and the RECON (retrospective conversion) program aimed at placing older-than-current publications on MARC tape. It is believed that Cataloging in Publication (CIP), a program funded in the last days of the previous fiscal year, will take its place beside MARC and RECON as an important milestone in library work.²⁰

On page two of the *Report of the Librarian of Congress, 1971* appears an enthusiastic look at the Council-initiated and supported program. It reads in part: "Selection of the year's notable developments frequently depends upon the point of view. In addition to the third building, Cataloging in Publication and the changeover of the Legislative Reference Service to the Congressional Research Service have perhaps the most widespread consequences.

"Benefits of the program to libraries are obvious. With the professional cataloging decisions printed in the book, a trained typist can prepare the cards and a book can be ready for the shelves within record time after its arrival in a given library. Reductions in cataloging costs, which may amount to twice as much as the cost of the book itself, are of paramount importance. Another benefit, which has not been as thoroughly emphasized, is the importance of the data to private collectors or to extremely small libraries that have no professional librarian. Further benefits will accrue from the availability of cataloging data in machine-readable form (MARC tapes) at a very early stage in book production."²¹

In the *CIP Progress Report No. 2* (July 1972), the Library of Congress Processing Department notes that 6,500 titles were processed in the first year, 5,200 of which moved through the department between Jan. 1 and June 30. Over 200 publishers are cooperating in the program and more are signing up. In August 1971, *Publishers Weekly* (PW) began

²⁰ XV:23-24.

²¹ *Annual Report of the Librarian of Congress for the Fiscal Year Ending June 30, 1971* (Washington: Government Printing Office, 1972).

utilizing CIP data when Library of Congress catalog cards were not available at the time a CIP title was received by PW for listing in its "Weekly Record."

A "Selected Bibliography on Cataloging in Publication" appears in the *CIP Progress Report No. 2*. It lists 36 items (cumulative to May 1972).²²

**A regional
cooperative
project**

Cooperation among libraries is a vital component of any national system. A Council grant this year to the Southwestern Library Association (SWLA) was for the purpose of encouraging a regional effort by the state librarians and library associations of Texas, Louisiana, Arkansas, Oklahoma, Arizona, and New Mexico. The grant, together with funds and services contributed by SWLA members, made it possible to establish and staff the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE). During its first year SLICE emphasized three program goals:

1. Extending to the six SWLA states the use of MARC-based services (MARC-O) developed by the Oklahoma Department of Libraries.
2. Developing a strategy for continuing education for all levels of library staff members in the SLICE area.
3. Initiating and stimulating regional planning and exchange of ideas among the librarians of the six states.

Good progress has been made in all areas. The SLICE Office has played an important role in initiating and implementing cooperative programs and in promoting effective communication among the members, all of whom are enthusiastic about the prospects for the future.

In general

Not all of the Council's efforts on behalf of libraries are through grants. Through staff participation in such national policy-making committees as the Committee on Scientific and Technical Information (COSATI) and in a special group charged with reviewing COSATI's operations and making recommendations as to its future, it has been possible to include a constructive library viewpoint in discussions destined to affect the national attitudes which in turn will affect libraries and their development.

A list of CLR national library services projects active in 1971-1972 follows:

²² Library of Congress Processing Department, *Cataloging in Publication Progress Report No. 2*, July 1972.

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for the publication of a new compilation of federal and state legislation to supplant a long obsolete second edition of <i>American Library Laws</i> , and for biennial supplements. The fourth supplement covering 1969-70 was published in the fall of 1971. Receipts from sales will be used for a fourth edition and supplements. [\$10,500 – 1963]	—————	—————
American Library Association , for preparation of a second decennial supplement to <i>American Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide</i> which was published in 1972 [\$4,000 – 1971]	—————	\$ 1,537
Association of Research Libraries , to supplement existing funds being used for completion of the National Serials Pilot Project [\$19,107 – 1971]	—————	—————
Indiana University Foundation , to enable Mildred Lowell to assemble case studies in a variety of areas of interest to the library administrator for publication. The fourth book in the series, <i>Management of Libraries – Vol. IV</i> , was published by The Scarecrow Press, Inc., in late 1971 [\$12,000 – 1967]	—————	[\$11]
Library of Congress , to support the Library's Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying. [\$58,376 – 1969]	—————	[\$4,588]
Library of Congress , for a continuation of the RECON project aimed at converting 85,000 (1968-69) English language monograph titles and 5,000 other selected titles to machine-readable form. [\$200,959 – 1970]	—————	—————
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , to continue a program of controlled experiments within the Intrex Project aimed at establishing characteristics and specifications for future library information and retrieval systems. [\$400,000 – 1971]	—————	100,000
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , toward continuation of Project Intrex.	\$400,000	\$300,000
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , for the establishment of a model engineering library as part of Project Intrex. The project has received a new grant for its continuation. [\$150,000 – 1970]	—————	32,750
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , continuance of the Model Engineering Library project.	71,000	17,750
National Academy of Sciences , for the appraisal of library and information system research and experimentation involving computers. [\$50,920 – 1970]	—————	5,920
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as a matching grant to be used with an NEH grant of \$200,000 to launch the Library of Congress' new program of Cataloging in Publication. [\$200,000 – 1971]	—————	—————

National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds toward a \$650,000 combined Council-NEH grant to the Stanford University Libraries to enable them to complete the basic development of the BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Libraries On-Line Time-Sharing) system and bring it to operational status at Stanford University.	325,000	325,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds for \$800,000 joint Council-NEH grant to University of Chicago for development and operational testing of a data management system at the library. [\$400,000 – 1970]	—————	—————
New England Board of Higher Education (NEBHE), to test the transferability of the Ohio College Library Center's (OCLC) computer-based bibliographic system to other libraries.	53,589	24,000
New England Board of Higher Education (NEBHE), for a technical and user audit of the New England Library Information Network (NELINET) cataloging support sub-system. [\$24,000 – 1971]	—————	10,000
Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), assistance toward purchase of equipment for the development of a computerized regional library system. [\$14,113 – 1970]	—————	—————
Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), to aid in developing and activating a computer-based, on-line, shared cataloging system.	75,000	20,000
Southwestern Library Association, to further interlibrary cooperation and planning in the states of Arizona, Arkansas, Louisiana, New Mexico, Oklahoma, and Texas. Entitled Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE), the project will provide centralized planning, development, and coordination of educational and other library activities in the region.	25,000	17,250
U. S. Army, Office, Chief of Engineers, to investigate the present characteristics of, and relationships between, technical libraries and other (extra-library) information storage, analysis, and retrieval systems, and libraries. Two reports have been prepared and published under the grant: <i>Extra-Library Information Programs in Selected Federal Agencies</i> by O. B. Conway, Jr., in 1970, and <i>Interface of Technical Libraries with other Information Systems</i> by Alan M. Rees in 1971. [\$20,000 – 1969]	—————	—————
United States Book Exchange (USBE), to provide one year of assistance so that USBE may restore its staff to approximately the 1969 level as recommended in a special report [\$48,450 – 1971]	—————	30,000
University of Lancaster, England, to carry on fundamental research on factors affecting the use of library service with the hope that appropriate findings will aid libraries to become more responsive to their constituencies. [\$37,500 – 1971]	—————	18,000

<p>University of North Carolina, to underwrite a portion of the expenses of the American National Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z-39 and its subcommittees as they work toward standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities. Equal funds are provided by the National Science Foundation. [\$61,275—1970]</p>	<p>—————</p>	<p>20,000</p>
<p>NATIONAL LIBRARIES TOTALS, 1971-72</p>	<p>\$949,589</p>	<p>\$917,608</p>

the public library

*Counselling
in connection
with CLEP
program*

These have been more than ordinarily difficult times for the public library in the United States. Changing expectations and changing clientele have required it to make a serious effort to find and understand itself. Who are its publics? What are their needs? What new goals should be added to the old?

An awareness of these problems by the Council, and the availability of matching funds from the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), resulted in a Council grant to NEH in the fall of 1970 toward a significant study effort by the Public Library Association (PLA).²³

Strategy for Change

In March 1972 the American Library Association (ALA) published the completed PLA report, *A Strategy for Public Library Change*. Its 84 pages examine societal forces and the library of the past 20 years and today before drawing conclusions and making recommendations—the basic “strategy for change.” These read in part:

1. There is a widespread lack of recognition of existing strengths and of the potential for full development of the public library as a community asset among the public at large, even among libraries of all types, including the public library.
2. There are gaps in what is known about the public library as an institution and about its performance which require research and experimentation demonstration, development of prototypes.
3. Much of the research and experimentation which has been completed is little known or has not been applied through demonstration, development of prototypes.
4. There is an urgent need for concentration on training and retraining of practitioners—those presently performing and those who will follow—to enable them to know how to establish goals for individual libraries, how to develop libraries which will continually change with society and perform effectively in the community.²⁴

Increased services for NYC

Conclusion number one, based on discussions by public library leaders cooperating with the Public Library Association in conducting its study, helped provide the rationale for the Council on Library Re-

²³ XV:13.

²⁴ Public Library Association, *A Strategy for Public Library Change* (Chicago: American Library Association, 1972).

sources' decision to make a grant of \$300,000 to the Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, Inc., toward an ambitious, unique "citizens' information centers" program budgeted at \$10 million. Another urgent consideration was the need to seek a way to reverse the anti-library syndrome found now in most large urban areas by making the library important to the citizen in terms of his own requirements.

The \$300,000 represents a portion of the \$2½ million the City of New York must raise in order to qualify for \$7½ million in federal funds. The information centers would be located in branch libraries throughout the city, and would be responsive to the needs of all citizens, including those groups mentioned in the ALA/PLA report.

The Council has made this somewhat unusual grant in the belief that traditional uses of the library will not be adversely affected by the enlargement of its service through the information centers. Rather it is hoped that the person who comes to the library initially to seek information about personal or local problems will soon come to see and make use of the library in its more customary role.

In its "News Report - 1971," the January 1972 *Library Journal* predicted that the project "could make library history overnight" - if additional matching funds are found and the project launched.²⁵

The public library and continuing education

Since 1971 the Council, the College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB), and the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) have provided support for the Dallas (Texas) Public Library's Independent Study Project, geared to assisting individuals interested in gaining college credit through CEEB's College Level Examination Program (CLEP).²⁶

Faculty members of Southern Methodist University have prepared guides for the study fields included in CLEP, and the University is also conducting an ongoing evaluation of the project. A number of other colleges and universities in the Dallas area have indicated that they will accept for course credit passing scores made by CLEP students in examinations.

At the end of the two-year program in September 1973, it is hoped that much will have been learned about the ways that public libraries can serve as a focal point in nontraditional study.

Public libraries of San Diego, St. Louis, and Miami have also been active in promoting individual study programs leading to CLEP examinations and college credit. To benefit from their knowledge, along with that accumulated through the Dallas experiment, the Council cooperated with CEEB in underwriting a one-day meeting in New York City of librarians from these institutions to discuss their experiences with CLEP.

²⁵ Karl Nyren, "News Report - 1971," *Library Journal* 97 (January 1, 1972).

²⁶ XV:13-14.

**User study
in Brooklyn
completed**

The fifteenth *Annual Report* told of a grant by the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities for a study to determine who uses the public library in a black community and to identify the factors that lead to nonuse.²⁷ Hardy Franklin, former staff member of the Brooklyn Public Library who became a full-time doctoral candidate at the Rutgers University Graduate School of Library Science, has completed his investigation of Brooklyn's Bedford-Stuyvesant area and submitted his report.

As would be expected, the results revealed a strong interest among users in Bedford-Stuyvesant in the availability of materials about blacks. The study also showed that young adults were more frequent users than older adults, females greater users than males, and single persons more than married or widowed. Although library use increased with advances in education and income, there was no evidence that degree of use can be predicted from a knowledge of a respondent's occupation.

A list of CLR public library projects active in 1971-72 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, Inc. , for the creation of citizens' information centers in New York City's branch libraries. The Council grant represents a portion of the \$2½ million the City of New York must raise in order to qualify for \$7½ million in federal funds.	\$300,000	-----
College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) , to co-sponsor with CEEB a one-day conference for public libraries participating in the College Level Examination Program (CLEP).	690	\$ 690
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as a matching grant with NEH for the study of adult public library users in the Bedford-Stuyvesant area by the Graduate School of Library Science of Rutgers University. [\$2,700 – 1971]	-----	-----
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as a matching grant with NEH to the Public Library Association of the American Library Association to conduct a study of the impact of changes in libraries. The two associations published <i>A Strategy for Public Library Change</i> in March 1972. [\$12,096 – 1971]		
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , to match one-half of an NEH \$50,000 grant. The College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB), also provided \$25,000 for the Dallas (Texas) Public Library program to investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study. [\$25,000 – 1971]	-----	-----
PUBLIC LIBRARY TOTALS, 1971-72	\$300,690	\$ 690

²⁷ XV:12-13.

Mr. 8.
Luce. 9.

Cest de saint pere la postre

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Et disoit lou quel dient les genz
a estre fil de la fame. Et il li respo
durent. Il un dient. Elve. li autre
Geremie. li autre Jehan bautist
ou un des wophetes. Et ihesus

archives and special collections

The concerns of the archivist and curator do not differ greatly from those of other librarians. All must deal with the problems that arise from the need to acquire, preserve, and handle large quantities of materials in such a way that they will be useful and accessible to researchers and scholars. Thus all the Council's grants will, it is hoped, be of assistance in meeting some of the needs of these special groups. But special groups have special requirements as well, and in the year covered by this report work has gone forward on 19 Council grants directed specifically toward archivists, curators of special collections, and their clientele.

**National
Archives
reports
on SPINDEX**

Of particular help to U. S. archivists will be the forthcoming publication of the report on the National Archives and Records Service's (NARS) SPINDEX II (Selective Permuted Indexing) project. The purpose of the Council-funded project was "the creation of a software package that would be potentially useful to both large and small repositories and would, if no modifications were made to the programs, assure institutions that their data in machine-readable form is compatible with the data of other institutions using the same programs."²⁸

²⁸ XII:11.

In order to test the program NARS used a small file to produce an index to the Guide to Cartographic Records in the National Archives. Approximately 5,000 entries were converted into machine-readable form and transferred to magnetic tape. A few modifications were necessary to make the system satisfactory from a programming standpoint, and it is now available for use with collections of almost any size.

The National Archives is at the present time using SPINDEX II to assist in the preparation of a new microfilm catalog, to design finding aids and indexes to the Captured German Records, and to produce a cumulative index to the "Journals of the Continental Congress."

**Manuals on
photographs
and care of
manuscript
collections**

A new Council grant to the American Association for State and Local History (AASLH) will finance the writing and publication of a manual on the collection, care, and use of photographs. The project recognizes the value of photographs as visual evidence of past events, places, and people, as well as the lack of technical information on the preservation of these materials.

Robert A. Weinstein, vice president of Ward-Ritchie Press, will be the author. He will use his broad knowledge and experience in dealing with photographs to develop a manual which treats the needs and techniques of collecting, arranging, cataloging, conserving, filing, and using photographs. Appropriate procedures will be included for daguerreotypes, tintypes, nitrate films, glass negatives, and other varied forms. Although primarily designed to assist the small historical museum or library, the book should aid larger institutions and private collections as well.

An earlier Council-supported project in cooperation with AASLH, for the preparation of a manual on the care of manuscript collections, was resumed in October 1971 after suspension for almost a year. Original project director Joseph Wheeler's death in late 1970 caused the delay. New project director Kenneth W. Duckett, archivist of Southern Illinois University, has prepared a draft of the first part of the manual, and is hoping to complete the entire manuscript for publication in late 1973.

**Law library
statistics**

Under a Council grant which extends to June 30, 1975, the American Association of Law Libraries is collecting and evaluating law library statistics and publishing the findings in *Law Library Journal*.²⁹ In the past fiscal year, this activity has resulted in reports on law libraries serving the local bar and court, law school libraries, and law library salaries.

²⁹ XIII:37-38.

Referring to this activity as "one of its most important projects," the Association plans to survey government law libraries and law firm libraries during the upcoming year.

**American
Studies
marketing
survey**

The Institute of United States Studies in London received a grant in fiscal 1972 for a market survey to determine the need for an American Studies bibliography. The degree of interest shown in such a publication will determine whether the Institute should consider the actual establishment of a machine-readable catalog aimed at production of U. S. Studies bibliographies on a regular, self-supporting basis.

Work has been completed on a 1970 grant to the National Central Library in London for preparing and circulating lists of recently acquired American titles in the humanities and social sciences.³⁰ General conclusion of project personnel was that the more frequent promotion of American books resulted in a substantial percentage increase in the demand for them. Part of the report on the two-year project appears in the April 1972 *ncl newsletter*.³¹ It remains to be seen whether the library will continue the printing and distribution of the popular American titles accession lists without outside support.

**Guides to
special
collections**

Several Council grants should prove helpful to scholars as they attempt to locate materials in their special areas of interest. In progress now are projects scheduled to result in guides to art reference books and to social science resources.³² Work is proceeding also on grants made for the identification of regional archives and manuscript repositories in Russia, and the evaluation of music libraries in Spain, France, Portugal, and England.³³

**Duplicating
rare
materials**

Two interesting projects concerned with duplicating rare materials have been completed at Dartmouth College and the University of Pennsylvania.³⁴ The Dartmouth College Library has made available microfilm editions of such rare materials as presidential election campaign documents for the years 1868-1900, scrapbooks covering the career of American novelist Winston Churchill, and papers of sculptor Augustus Saint-Gaudens. Pennsylvania's efforts at developing a Middle Atlantic States Archive of Medieval Manuscripts on Microfilm

³⁰ XIV: 43.

³¹ A. Allardyce, "An Experiment with Accessions Lists for American Books," *ncl newsletter*, No. 12 (April 1972).

³² XV:36.

³³ XV:39.

³⁴ XV:31-32; XIII:37.

resulted in the acquisition of about 160 manuscripts from 40 libraries in ten countries. They represent topics in the fields of chronicle and heraldry, Arthurian and Chaucerian studies, romances, and drama, paleography and lexicography. The Council-sponsored project is the pilot effort of what it is hoped will be a considerably larger program.

A list of CLR archives and special collections projects active in 1971-72 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Association for State & Local History , toward the preparation of a book on the collection, care and use of photographs.	\$ 10,000	\$ 1,700
American Association of State and Local History , for the preparation of a manual on the care of manuscript collections. [\$34,604 – 1970]	-----	2,285
American Association of Law Libraries , to conduct an annual statistical survey of law library resources in the United States and Canada. [\$20,000 – 1968]	-----	2,000
Etta Arntzen , for a revision of the original 1959 edition of Mary W. Chamberlin's <i>Guide to Art Reference Books</i> . [\$8,000 – 1971]	-----	3,200
Australian National Library , to assist in the travel of Asian librarians to the 28th International Congress of Orientalists in Canberra, Australia, and the publication of papers presented. [\$20,000 – 1971]	-----	-----
Dartmouth College , for the coordination of a program for producing microfilm editions of rare research materials. [\$8,800 – 1970]	-----	-----
Institute of United States Studies (London), toward a preliminary survey of the market for an American Studies bibliography.	5,000	1,100
National Archives and Records Service , to apply a computer indexing and composition system to manuscript/archival materials. A history of the project with thorough documentation is being printed by the Government Printing Office under the title, <i>Spindex II: Reports and System Documentation</i> . [\$40,000 – 1967]	-----	-----
National Central Library (London), toward the support of continued publication and increased distribution of acquisition lists of American titles for loan in the United Kingdom. [\$15,000 – 1970]	-----	-----

National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as matching grant to NEH for a program at Stanford University to achieve bibliographic control of secondary literature relevant to modern Chinese society. [\$5,000—1970]	-----	----
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , toward the preparation of <i>Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids</i> . [\$12,739—1971]	-----	----
Carol A. Nemeyer , to identify, describe, and analyze the activities of the U. S. scholarly-reprint publisher. Her work <i>Scholarly Reprint Publishing in the United States</i> was published by R. R. Bowker Co. in 1972. [\$2,813—1970]	-----	455
Newberry Library , to conduct a feasibility study for the MARC cataloging of pre-1900 maps in midwestern collections. Conclusions reached: production of a 75,000-item union catalog of pre-1900 maps in midwestern collections is feasible and desirable. [\$2,350—1970]	-----	[\$525]
Rare Books Conference on Facsimiles , to enable Filming Standards Subcommittee members to attend two meetings to produce a set of physical standards for reproduction of materials held by member libraries. [\$2,000—1971]	-----	--
Society of American Archivists , to assist Ernst Posner to prepare his manuscript, <i>Archives in the Ancient World</i> for publication. The book was published by Harvard University Press in 1972, with a dedication note to the Council's Verner W. Clapp. [\$3,000—1967]	-----	--
Society of American Archivists , toward the expenses of a committee to examine the programs of the Society in an effort to improve its service to members and to scholars. [\$3,500—1971]	-----	--
University of California at San Diego , to assist in the preparation of 2nd edition of <i>Sources of Information in the Social Sciences</i> . [\$4,910—1970]	-----	2,016
University of Iowa , to undertake an investigation of the administration, services, and collections of music libraries in Spain, Portugal, France and England. The finished product will be Part III of a "Directory of Music Research Libraries." [\$1,425—1971]	-----	1,100
University of Pennsylvania , for a pilot project in collecting medieval source materials on microfilm to be used by scholars of the University of Pennsylvania and other universities. [\$8,500—1969]	-----	-----
ARCHIVES AND SPECIAL COLLECTIONS TOTALS 1971-72	\$ 15,000	\$ 13,331

international cooperation

“Toward an International Cataloging Code” was a subhead in the Council’s first *Annual Report* 15 years ago. The story that followed described the dilemma of the world’s librarians, “condemned to cataloging afresh those publications of every other country which they acquire, as though the country of origin were not already doing the job, and possibly better.” That same report tells of the Council’s first grant, to the American Library Association (ALA), “toward international standardization of cataloging—to assist ALA to participate in meeting of German Library Association, Lubeck, Germany.”³⁵

With this and dozens of related grants, the Council has encouraged what the current president of the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), Herman Liebaers of Belgium, refers to as Universal Bibliographic Control. IFLA was the recipient of many of these grants, a number of which supported international meetings and provided travel funds for selected participants.

To strengthen IFLA

In 1971 the Council moved to improve upon this pattern. A \$100,000 grant was made to IFLA for use over a three-year period during which the organization was to take steps toward constructive reorganization and self-support.³⁶ This investment began paying dividends almost immediately. For example, in 1971-72:

- Membership in IFLA is up 25 percent, and international participation in the organization is growing with its strengthening of professional staff.
- Cooperation with two other key coordinating organizations, UNESCO and FID (Fédération Internationale de Documentation), is extending into several areas.
- More than 700 participants from 60 countries attended the 1971 IFLA General Council Meeting in Liverpool, England. Theme of the meeting: “Organization of the Library Profession.”

³⁵ I:26-27.

³⁶ XV:37.

- During the year the IFLA Board and staff worked out a new dues structure aimed at making IFLA self-supporting by the time the Council's grant is ended. This was scheduled for presentation to the membership at the August 1972 General Meeting in Budapest.

To strengthen international cataloging

That same year the Council made another three-year grant to IFLA with significant implications for the international library community. With the help of the \$54,000 award, IFLA established a permanent secretariat for its Committee on Cataloguing.³⁷ A strengthened publications program, highly important in a specialized international effort of this sort, is one of the several notable accomplishments of the secretariat. *International Cataloguing*, published quarterly at a modest subscription rate, provides for the first time a forum for feedback and discussion as well as dissemination of information. Catalogers now know well in advance about planning for and development of standards that will directly affect their work. Highly technical international information on bibliographic and cataloging topics is now readily available.

International Book Year

The Council and IFLA are cooperating fully with UNESCO in promoting International Book Year—1972 (IBY). The Council's major contribution is in the form of partial support of a U. S. secretariat to coordinate this country's IBY activities. Basic objectives of International Book Year are:

- The encouragement of authorship and translation;
- The improved production and circulation of books, including the development of libraries, especially in the developing countries;
- Promotion of the reading habit;
- Strengthening the usefulness of books in the service of education, international understanding, and peaceful co-operation.

International standards, serials

In the area of international standards for libraries, documentation, and related publishing practices, three major agencies are active. They are the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), the International Federation for Documentation (FID), and the International Standards Organization (ISO). While international standards are being worked out, some new organizations are being developed to apply them. Of course, new standards have major effect on existing libraries,

³⁷ XV:37-38.

documentation centers, and related publishing. Some time ago, the Council perceived a need for action across all of these organizations: first to ensure that those to be affected participated in the formulation of standards, and second to see that they were kept informed of standards progress. There was also a requirement to ensure that, where the efforts of these organizations overlapped, the results were compatible. The independent nature of the Council gives it a unique opportunity to perform this kind of service.

A good example of how the Council can act as catalyst and diplomat in standards work lies in the recent development and application of the International Standard Serial Number (ISSN). The Council supports Standards Committee Z-39, where the U. S. standard for serial numbering was formulated.³⁸ CLR staff worked with librarians and others to get the draft standard accepted in this country. When Z-39 entered the U. S. standard as a candidate for adoption as the international standard, final action on which will take place in 1973, Council staff participated in the international work. When the International Serials Data System (ISDS) was developed to assume responsibility for the ISSN, a Council staff member was among the technical advisors to the ISDS. Since Council staff also provide technical advice and assistance to the U. S. National Serials Data Program and in the development of regional serials systems, there was ample opportunity to enhance compatibility in and acceptance of this standards work.

Two other activities where this kind of work is performed by Council staff are the International Standard Bibliographic Description for Serials and the Serial Article Identification Code, both in process at this writing.

A list of CLR international projects active in 1971-72 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Columbia University , for a study of the acquisition of foreign publications with the use of U. S. counterpart funds and their distribution and handling upon receipt. Eight countries covered by P.L. 480 were included in the study. [\$3,767 - 1969]	\$ ———	\$ 21
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , for travel funds for the speakers participating in the symposium, "Reading in a Changing World," at the August 1972 General Meeting.	1,500	—————
International Federation of Library Associations , to enable IFLA to institute reforms and operate at an effective professional level during the three years required to complete restructuring of dues so that the organization may become self-supporting. [\$100,000 - 1971]	—————	36,633

³⁸ XV:21-22.

International Federation of Library Associations , to establish a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloging as a center to promote and coordinate the international standardization of cataloging practices. [\$54,000—1971]	—————	12,600
National Book Committee , for partial support of a secretariat for the United States' participation in International Book Year.	25,000	10,000
Travel Funds to enable librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to attend appropriate meetings abroad which they might otherwise be unable to attend. [\$5,000—1971]	—————	2,905
Travel Funds , additional funds for above purposes.	5,000	647
Travel Funds , to enable important foreign librarians to visit the United States, when their presence is essential for the purpose of carrying out selected tasks. [\$5,000—1970]	—————	1,000
INTERNATIONAL TOTALS, 1971-72	\$31,500	\$63,806

preservation and library technology

A significant number of the Council's grants have been addressed to the preservation and conservation of the library's major resources—books, documents, periodicals, reports, etc., and the materials on which they are printed and in which they are bound. Also of considerable concern have been the preservation and durability of such related equipment as index cards, file cabinets, library furniture, microfilm and associated equipment.

The Council's interest in this broad area dates back to its earliest days. In 1958 a Library Technology Program (LTP) was established within the American Library Association (ALA) and supported by the Council on a continuing basis through fiscal year 1971.³⁹ A few years after the establishment of LTP, in 1961, the Council assisted in the formation of the W. J. Barrow Laboratory for the investigation of problems relating to the preservation of books and other library materials.⁴⁰ In the years since, the Laboratory's support has come almost completely

³⁹ IV:20-21.

⁴⁰ VII:20-23.

from CLR, although, with the Council's encouragement, the Laboratory has recently begun to perform work under contract with organizations having similar interests.

**Barrow
Laboratory
progress**

The single most valuable contribution of the Barrow Laboratory to date is its development of specifications for a permanent/durable (P/D) book paper capable of manufacture from chemical wood pulp, within the normal price range of book papers. Books and periodicals printed on P/D paper appear to be far less subject to deterioration over the years than are those that have been published on other papers since the mid-nineteenth century, when acidic alum rosin sizing was introduced into the manufacture of paper. Since a large part of every library's collection consists of books printed on this nondurable paper, their preservation constitutes an important and costly problem.

Recently the Barrow Laboratory has been developing a process to deacidify paper by gaseous diffusion. Previous work in this area, by the Laboratory and others, has accomplished a page-by-page deacidification of single books. The present process, however, treats a number of books at one time. Books thus treated have shown significantly less deterioration than untreated ones when exposed to an artificial aging process.

Important work has been accomplished also in other areas:

- Study of old papers.
- Revision of specifications for permanent/durable paper (jointly with the Library of Congress).
- Effect of storage temperature on paper.
- Strengthening of weak papers.
- Effect of humidity on paper stored at high temperature.
- New method for nondestructive surface pH measurement on paper.

In addition, the Laboratory plans in the coming year to begin work on the development of specifications for coated permanent/durable paper, determining maximum safe alkalinity for paper exposed to a range of chemical conditions, and testing groundwood content paper for permanence/durability.

**Preservation
Office in
Library of
Congress**

Complementing the activities of the Barrow Laboratory—and in some instances working jointly with it—is the Library of Congress Preservation Research Office, established with some financial support from the Council in 1970.⁴¹ By agreement with the Library of Congress, the

⁴¹ XIV:34.

Council has a consultative role in planning the Preservation Office's program—an important factor in approaching the Council's goal of avoiding wasteful duplication and achieving cooperative effort in this as in other areas of research for libraries. By the end of the fiscal year, the Preservation Research Office was in full operation, with several significant projects under way.

**Research
in Italy**

Two additional grants for research in preservation and conservation were made during the year, both of them to individuals working through Italian institutions.

Margaret Hey, an English chemist, is carrying out a series of experiments at the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome on the effects of various bleaches on paper; she is also evaluating heatset paper tissues (the name given to a material specially made for the mending of paper by dry application). Heatset tissues were first developed and used by the Cockerell Institute in England and were then further developed for use on books damaged in the Florence, Italy, flood of 1966.

Anthony Cains, a bookbinder who had been in charge of the restoration activities at the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Florence (BNCF), has received a Council grant for developing a manual which describes the restoration methods presently employed by BNCF, how they were evolved during a time of crisis, and why there were chosen in preference to others. Mr. Cains writes of his project: "The manual places emphasis throughout on the importance of the book in its historical setting so that nothing is done which renders the restored book an anachronism, and on the importance of the continued functionality of the book after restoration. As many working alternatives as possible are described at every stage, and the restorer is encouraged by constant reference to other sectors of the work to appreciate the fundamental interrelationship between the work of one department and another in determining the quality of the finished work."

**Automatic
catalog card
filming
camera**

In the past few years many academic libraries have microfilmed their card catalogs as a hedge against national disaster and vandalism and as a means of providing inexpensive copies of the catalog to other local and remote locations. Unfortunately the effectiveness of microfilm copying of catalog cards is critically limited by the available automatic cameras, all of which were developed for other applications having less stringent requirements.

As a part of the Council's program of improving the utility of microforms in libraries, a contract has been entered into with Mega System Design of Toronto, Canada, for development of an operational prototype of an automatic catalog card filming camera. Design goals of

the camera include high resolution images, speed of at least 120 cards per minute, highly reliable feeding of cards of varying thickness and physical condition, and high density recording on 16mm film. The camera will be tested in a normal operating environment at a major university library before its delivery in late winter 1973. It is expected that the first operational use will be at the Joint University Libraries at Vanderbilt University.

LTP projects, publications

Although ALA's Library Technology Program is no longer receiving direct operational support from the Council, three specific project grants were made to LTP in 1971-72. These are for performance testing of plastic card catalog trays with wood fronts, evaluation of the effectiveness of film rejuvenation treatments, and performance testing of a new low-cost catalog card cabinet.

Two earlier grants to LTP have resulted in publications this year: *The Restoration of Leather Bindings* by Bernard C. Middleton (in its "Conservation of Library Materials" series) and *Wood Chairs* (in its "Portfolio" series).⁴²

A list of CLR preservation and technology projects active in 1971-72 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for performance testing of plastic card catalog trays with wood fronts.	\$ 10,220	\$ 4,610
American Library Association , to evaluate the effectiveness of film rejuvenation treatments.	3,709	2,709
American Library Association , for performance testing of a new low-cost catalog card cabinet.	4,015	1,750
American Library Association , LTP Director's Discretionary Fund. [\$15,000—1969]	—————	2,505
American Library Association , for a chair-testing program aimed at identifying specific data on which sound choices of chairs can be made. [\$62,750—1968]	—————	11,375
American Library Association , toward preparation and issuance by the Library Technology Program of five publications that will constitute a comprehensive manual on the care and repair of books and other library materials [\$30,000—1968]	—————	—————
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , for operation of the Laboratory for the period August 1, 1969, to August 15, 1971. Project is continuing under new grant. [\$199,660—1969]	—————	18,905

⁴² Bernard C. Middleton, *The Restoration of Leather Bindings* (Chicago: American Library Association, 1972). Library Technology Program, Portfolio Series, *Wood Chairs* (Chicago: American Library Association 1971).

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , continued operation of the Laboratory for the period August 16, 1971, to July 31, 1973.	265,350	93,548
Anthony Cairns , to complete a workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts based on the practices of the Restoration Department of the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, Italy.	4,350	2,471
Margaret Hey , to investigate book and archival paper restoration techniques along scientific lines already under way in the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome, Italy.	10,500	6,224
Imperial College of Science and Technology (London), for research on the conservation of library materials. [\$75,240—1969]	—————	7,036
Betty Jo Irvine , to prepare and edit a manual for librarians and curators on use of slides and slide projectors. Awaiting publication. [\$4,389—1971]	—————	3,379
Levittown Public Library , to test the effectiveness of an electronic book-theft detection system. [\$8,990—1971]	—————	2,000
Library of Congress , assistance in equipping a preservation research office in the Library. [\$95,000—1970]	—————	23,550
Mega System Design , development of an automatic library card camera.	23,400	11,700
New York Public Library , to determine the feasibility of putting the NYPL Research Libraries' retrospective and prospective catalogs on microfilm. [\$10,000—1971]	—————	4,000
Royal College of Art (London), for the study of early limp vellum binding practices for purposes of conservation. [\$9,720—1970]	—————	5,691
Tulane University Library , conversion of a computer-taped catalog to microfilm and the testing of user acceptance. [\$4,000—1971]	—————	1,889
PRESERVATION AND TECHNOLOGY TOTALS, 1971-72	\$321,544	\$203,342

the profession

The Council's continuing awareness of the importance of the individual's contribution to even the largest and most complex of libraries has been the basis for two ongoing programs started in 1968:

- Surveys of the compensation structures of professional librarians in colleges and universities.
- The CLR Fellowship Program for midcareer librarians.

The ultimate goal of each program is to bring able people into the profession and to keep them there.

Second survey of academic librarians

The compensation surveys by Donald Cameron and Peggy Heim represent a first step in efforts to improve the economic condition of the profession by collecting reliable up-to-date information on salaries currently paid and on other forms of compensation.⁴³ In February 1972 their *How Well Are They Paid? Compensation Structures of Professional Librarians in College and University Libraries, 1970-71*, was published and distributed by the Council to the presidents and library directors of four-year institutions of higher education.⁴⁴ Its statistics tell much the same story as did those in the earlier survey for 1969-70—that academic library salaries are relatively low and there are not enough opportunities for advancement.

One difference noted in the two surveys was an increase in the number of professional librarians in the curator-bibliographer-specialist category in universities—an increase from 7 to 12 percent. However, even here salaries averaged but \$13,000 annually, about the same as assistant professors and library department heads in the institutions in which they serve. A third survey is expected to collect more varied information on specialists in the academic library field.

Fourth set of CLR Fellows

Now in its fourth year, the Council's Fellowship Program attempts to enhance the profession by offering midcareer librarians an opportunity similar to the traditional sabbatical enjoyed by their faculty colleagues.⁴⁵ Recipients of CLR Fellowships pursue approved projects of their own choosing while on a continuous leave of absence of at least three months.

Louis B. Wright, vice-chairman of the Council's Board of Directors and director emeritus of the Folger Shakespeare Library, is chairman of the Fellowship Committee. Other members are William S. Dix, librarian of Princeton University; Robert Vosper, librarian of the University of California at Los Angeles; and—ex officio—Fred C. Cole, president, Foster E. Mohrhardt, senior program officer, and Edith M. Lesser, secretary and treasurer of the Council.

All 1972 applications were first reviewed by a screening committee of eight prominent librarians—Edwin Castagna of the Enoch Pratt

⁴³ XV:17.

⁴⁴ Donald Cameron and Peggy Heim, *How Well Are They Paid, 1970-71* (Washington: Council on Library Resources, 1972).

⁴⁵ XV:17-19; XIV:44-46, XIII:41-42; XII:35.

Free Library, Mary Corning of the National Library of Medicine, Richard De Gennaro of the University of Pennsylvania, Paul Howard, former executive secretary of the Federal Library Committee, Father James Kortendick of the Catholic University of America, John Lorenz of the Library of Congress, A. P. Marshall of Eastern Michigan University, and Stephen McCarthy of the Association of Research Libraries.

In making the awards, the Fellowship Committee evaluates each proposal on its potential usefulness to the applicant, to his institution, and to the profession as a whole. Of the 77 awards made thus far, 24 fellows have completed their work, 23 are near completion, and 30 (the 1972 recipients) are at the beginning stages. Six of the completed programs have resulted in one or more journal articles each, and three others are expected to result in useful books. In addition, many of the fellows have reported their findings in speeches, seminars, and larger conferences of their colleagues. Whether related to their fellowship experience or not, eight recipients have been recently promoted to major library directorships or the equivalent.

In 1972, fellowships were awarded to these 30 librarians:

Patricia Andrews, Chief Librarian, National Archives Library, Washington, D. C. An investigation of the various ways that government publications are controlled in libraries that are designated depositories for United States government publications, and to acquire data on the scope of the collections.

John M. Bruer, Head of Acquisitions, University of Kentucky Library. To examine the procedures used by medium-sized academic libraries in creating a record of book funds and in accounting for materials received in order to determine the institution's objectives, methods, and future direction, with particular reference to the influence of reduced book budgets and/or Planning-Programming-Budgeting.

Lois Nabrit Clark, Head Librarian, Knoxville College, Tennessee. To visit ten academic libraries of varying size and complexity, six of which have converted from Dewey Decimal to Library of Congress Classification, in order to help formulate a decision on conversion for the Knoxville College Library.

John Young Cole, Technical Officer, Reference Department, Library of Congress, Washington, D. C. To complete research and begin writing a history of the idea of a national library in the United States during the 19th century.

Richard E. Combs, Head Librarian, Northbrook (Illinois) Public Library. A study of emerging patterns of service within and between public libraries in the U. S. and of changes attendant upon the great demographic shifts within metropolitan areas.

Andrea Claire Dragon, Librarian, Minneapolis Institute of Arts, Minnesota. A three-month administrative internship, divided between the University of Minnesota Library and the Hill Reference Library.

Ralph E. Ehrenberg, Assistant Director, Cartographic Archives, National Archives, Washington, D. C. A comprehensive survey and analysis of archival map repositories and their functions in the U. S., Canada, and England in order to develop basic guidelines for the care and servicing of cartographic archival records.

Katherine T. Emerson, Assistant to Director of Libraries, University of Massachusetts, Amherst. Development of qualitative and quantitative measures of reference service in selected university and research libraries, with particular emphasis on relations between varying staffing patterns and user satisfaction.

Elizabeth T. Fast, Director of Media Services, Groton, Connecticut, Public Schools. A study of the programs of preparation of school librarians and media specialists by graduate library schools in the area, and an exploration of possible cooperative efforts between public school systems and library schools.

Gordon E. Fretwell, Associate Director of the University Library, University of Massachusetts, Amherst. An investigation of the programs of user support a typical group of 15 U. S. colleges and universities provides graduate students in the humanities and social sciences through libraries and library-related services.

Guy G. Garrison, Professor and Dean, Graduate School of Library Science, Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. To investigate changing patterns in organization and services in representative urban public libraries and to assess the degree to which library schools and state library agencies are participating in research and development activities which guide, support, and evaluate these changes.

J. Myron Jacobstein, Law Librarian, Stanford University School of Law, California. A study of the impact of interdisciplinary studies on academic libraries, with particular reference to professional school libraries.

Richard J. Johnson, Director of Libraries, The Claremont Colleges, California. A study of joint library facilities at various colleges and universities.

W. David Laird, Jr., Associate Director of Libraries, University of Utah. An investigation of access to library collections of materials on microform, with a view to developing a plan for a national processing center for microforms.

Nolan Lushington, Director of Greenwich, Connecticut, Public Library. A study of middle-sized English public libraries, examining the relationships among services, staff, community, program, and building with a view to relating library trends in England to those in the U. S.

Maurice Marchant, Associate Professor of Library and Information Sciences, Brigham Young University, Utah. A field study of participative management in university libraries.

Susan K. Martin, Systems Librarian, Harvard University, Cambridge, Massachusetts. To study current trends in library automation and cooperation to determine short- and long-range expectations for the academic library community.

Ellis Mount, Science & Engineering Librarian, Columbia University, New York City. To observe and analyze the ways in which university science and engineering libraries are using and adapting their budgets, facilities, and staffing patterns in dealing with new aspects of technical information, in the face of more restrictive budgets.

Richard L. O'Keeffe, Librarian, Fondren Library, Rice University, Houston, Texas. To visit many of the medium-sized and a few large private university libraries in order to examine their response to the needs of local research organizations and industry for library resources and information.

Margaret A. Otto, Assistant Director of Reader Services, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. To study selected cooperative library programs on the local, regional, and national level in an effort to determine the appropriate role for each with respect to each other and with respect to research and academic libraries.

Robert E. Pfeiffer, Head, Graduate Social Sciences Library, University of California, Berkeley. Completion of a book with the tentative title "A Guide to Anthropology Reference," to be published in fall 1972 by the American Library Association.

Harold T. Pinkett, Chief, Natural Resources Branch, National Archives, Washington, D. C. A comparative study of accessioning activities in some representative public agencies in the United States and abroad.

George Piternick, Professor, School of Librarianship, University of British Columbia. An investigation of book storage practices in academic libraries, with emphasis on choice of storage methods and reasons for choice.

Donald L. Roberts, Head Music Librarian, Northwestern University, Evanston, Illinois. To study the most desirable methods of housing, preserving, and cataloging outstanding collections of music manuscripts.

Priscilla R. Scott, Head, Circulation Division, University of Victoria Library, British Columbia. To study college and university library collection sharing networks and the services available to students to determine whether a college and university regional library network is needed in British Columbia.

Ernest Siegel, Director, Central Library, Los Angeles Public Library. A survey of public central library services in Canadian and European metropolitan areas.

Alva W. Stewart, Associate Librarian, College of William and Mary, Williamsburg, Virginia. To determine the purposes of selected urban research centers in the U. S. and to explore how libraries of these centers are helping staff members to achieve these purposes.

Dorothy G. Whittemore, Head, Social Sciences Division, Tulane University Library, New Orleans, Louisiana. To study the use of U. S. government document collections in selected metropolitan libraries in order to determine ways of promoting utilization of these resources.

Fay Zipkowitz, Head, Information Processing Department, University of Massachusetts, Amherst. Five-month internship, divided between the Institute of Library Research at Berkeley and the Library of Congress MARC Office.

Martin J. Zonligt, Head of Extension & Outreach Services, Stanislaus County (California) Free Library. A survey and in-depth study of library and potential library services to migrant farmworkers and former migrants in the three West Coast states.

CLR commitments and payments under the Fellowship Program in 1971-72 are as follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM TOTALS, 1971-1972	\$ 80,041	\$ 59,043

grants and contracts, payments totals 1971-72

Grants and contracts and payments totals for 1971-72 are as follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
THE ACADEMIC LIBRARY	\$ 503,475	\$ 482,930
NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES	949,589	917,608
THE PUBLIC LIBRARY	300,690	690
ARCHIVES AND SPECIAL COLLECTIONS	15,000	13,331
INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION	31,500	63,606
PRESERVATION AND LIBRARY TECHNOLOGY	321,544	203,342
COUNCIL FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM	80,041	59,043
	<hr/>	<hr/>
GRAND TOTALS	\$2,201,839	\$1,740,750

verner w. clapp

1901-1972

Verner Warren Clapp, full-time consultant to the Council on Library Resources and its president from 1956 to 1967, died in an Alexandria, Va., hospital June 15, 1972. While Mr. Clapp had twice "retired" from career-pinnacle positions – in 1956 as Chief Assistant Librarian of Congress (he had served as acting Librarian of Congress in 1953-54) and in 1967 as president of the Council on Library Resources – he was active to the end in aiding in the solution of library problems.

The week before his death he received a special citation from the Special Libraries Association for his "continued encouragement and support of special librarianship." A year earlier he was featured in *Wilson Library Bulletin* (February 1971) as "Library Ombudsman – near omniscient defender of the good and true, scourge of the malignant and misleading." The Association of Research Libraries dubbed him "Librarian's Librarian" in 1967, and in the *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* (June 23, 1972) announcing his death, it was noted, "He had become, ultimately, the library world's da Vinci."

Representative tributes to Mr. Clapp follow:

Upon his retirement as Council president

Mr. Clapp has made the Council on Library Resources significant throughout the world. His imagination, ingenuity and extraordinary fund of information have enabled him to give precise and significant counsel concerning library problems on both sides of the Atlantic. Grants made under his administration have already profoundly influenced library development.

Whitney North Seymour, Chairman
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Accompanying Council's announcement of his death

Verner Clapp was as much a universal scholar and teacher as anyone I have ever known. He dedicated his limitless energy to his profession and to its improvement. To the last he pressed himself continuously to increase his own knowledge in order to serve his profession and his fellow men.

Fred C. Cole, President
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

At Library of Congress memorial

He was a joyous humanist. His ethics and his reason for being derived from that humanism. Not for him were the existential agonies of so many of our intellectuals today. He knew he was here to help society by good works in his chosen field of activity and to enjoy life, and for

him much of the enjoyment of life was in the doing of good work.

Frederick Wagman, Director
University of Michigan Library

**On receiving
special ARL
citation
in 1967**

Polymath and sage, chronicler of the past and seer of the future, counselor to the United Nations and to foreign governments, advisor to library organizations, scholarly associations, and to countless libraries, his influence both nationally and internationally has been immeasurable.

Association of Research Libraries

**On receiving
Joseph W.
Lippincott
Award in 1960**

In all of his activities his wide background, his abilities as a creative thinker, his warm personality, and his inexhaustible energy serve his profession and provide inspiration and encouragement to all who work toward the solution of the problems of librarianship.

American Library Association

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 10, 1972

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1972 and June 30, 1971, the expenses, income and changes in fund balance and the changes in cash and investments for the years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

**Statement of assets,
liabilities and fund balance**

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1972	1971
ASSETS		
Cash	\$ 225,138	\$ 265,297
Investments		
Savings account	11,964	3,566
Certificates of deposit, at cost of \$250,000 plus accrued interest	250,063	250,109
Accrued royalty income receivable	1,083	5,771
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 1)	3,976,461	1,061,035
Prepaid expenses and deposits	1,921	4,630
	<u>\$4,466,630</u>	<u>\$1,590,408</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Grants and contracts payable	\$1,603,170	\$1,217,694
Fellowships payable	89,155	84,861
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	27,885	38,342
	<u>1,720,210</u>	<u>1,340,897</u>
Fund balance (Note 2)	<u>2,746,420</u>	<u>249,511</u>
	<u>\$4,466,630</u>	<u>\$1,590,408</u>

Statement of expenses, income and changes in fund balance

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1972	1971
EXPENSES		
Program		
Grants and contracts	\$2,121,797	\$1,346,692
Fellowships	80,041	55,290
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants and fellowships awarded	<u>(71,319)</u>	<u>(149,982)</u>
	2,130,519	1,252,000
Compensation and employee benefits	163,003	175,821
Consultants' fees and expenses	40,096	48,985
Travel	16,780	12,876
Other	<u>3,729</u>	<u>2,552</u>
	<u>2,354,127</u>	<u>1,492,234</u>
Administrative		
Compensation and employee benefits	110,763	136,963
Rent	21,930	21,580
Professional services	7,005	13,435
Travel and meetings	11,407	13,859
Furniture and equipment	3,137	3,515
Printing and duplication	9,343	8,441
Office and other expense	<u>16,438</u>	<u>16,892</u>
	<u>180,023</u>	<u>214,685</u>
	<u>2,534,150</u>	<u>1,706,919</u>
INCOME FROM INVESTMENTS	21,234	48,361
INCOME FROM ROYALTIES (Note 3)	3,325	9,337
SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTED CONTRACT (Note 4)	<u>6,500</u>	
	<u>31,059</u>	<u>57,698</u>
EXCESS OF EXPENSES OVER INCOME	(2,503,091)	(1,649,221)
Fund balance, beginning of year	249,511	1,898,732
Add-Grant from The Ford Foundation (Note 1)	<u>5,000,000</u>	
Fund balance, end of year (Note 2)	<u><u>\$2,746,420</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 249,511</u></u>

**Statement of changes in
cash and investments**

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1972	1971
CASH RECEIPTS		
Receipts from The Ford Foundation	\$2,084,574	\$1,759,339
Income from investments and royalties	29,293	59,920
Grant, fellowship and other refunds	15,925	2,931
	<u>2,129,792</u>	<u>1,822,190</u>
CASH DISBURSEMENTS		
Program expense	1,974,560	2,164,660
Administrative expense	186,893	198,414
Employee travel advances	100	
	<u>2,161,553</u>	<u>2,363,074</u>
Decrease in cash	(31,761)	(540,884)
Decrease in accrued interest	(46)	(7,993)
Cash and investments, beginning of year	518,972	1,067,849
Cash and investments, end of year	<u>\$ 487,165</u>	<u>\$ 518,972</u>

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

1. The Ford Foundation Grants

Effective July 1, 1971, The Ford Foundation approved an additional \$5,000,000 grant to the Council for the continuation and expansion of the Council's program. The new grant agreement specifies that the remaining balance of a prior grant and the new grant are to be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of approximately \$2,000,000 for a three year period beginning July 1, 1971.

2. Appropriations of Fund Balance

At June 30, 1972, and June 30, 1971, \$389,903 and \$1,698,797, respectively, had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts. In addition, at those dates, \$94,150 and \$92,352, respectively, had been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each to be made at his discretion.

3. Royalties

On October 10, 1969, the Council entered an agreement for the publication of "Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries" developed under its sponsorship. It is the Council's intention to use royalties received from sale of this publication to fund the preparation of revisions and supplements to the work.

4. Settlement of Disputed Contract

In fiscal year 1972 the Council received \$6,500 in settlement of their claim against a grantee for an uncompleted contract.

Index to active CLR projects, 1971-72

In the fiscal year 1971-72 the Council on Library Resources made 26 new grants for projects and monitored 66 others which had been funded in earlier years. An index of institutional recipients cited in this report follows:

- Administration and Management Research
 - Association of New York City, Inc. 29
- American Association for State and Local History 34
- American Association of Law Libraries 34
- American Library Association 14, 23, 43
- Arntzen, Etta 34
- Association of American Colleges 14
- Association of Research Libraries 14, 23
- Australian National Library 34,
- Barrow, W. J., Research Laboratory, Inc. 43, 44
- Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc. 14
- Cains, Anthony 44
- Cataloging in Publication (see NEH) 23
- College Entrance Examination Board 29
- Columbia University 14, 39
- Consortium of Upper Middle Atlantic University Libraries 14
- Cornell University 15
- Dallas, City of (see NEH) 29
- Dartmouth College 34
- Hey, Margaret 44
- Howard University 13
- Imperial College of Science and Technology 44
- Indiana University Foundation 23
- Institute of United States Studies 34
- International Federation of Library Associations 39, 40
- Irvine, Betty Jo 44
- Levittown Public Library 44
- Library of Congress 23
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology 23
- Mathematica, Inc. 15
- Mega Systems Design Limited 44
- Michigan State University 15
- National Academy of Sciences 23
- National Archives and Records Service 34
- National Book Committee 40
- National Central Library (England) 34
- National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) 15, 23, 24, 29, 34, 35
- Nemeyer, Carol A. 35
- Newberry Library 35
- New England Board of Higher Education 24
- New York City (see Administration and Management Research Association) 29
- New York Public Library 44
- North Carolina Central University 13
- North Carolina State Board of Higher Education 15
- Ohio College Library Center 24
- Ohio State University Research Foundation 15
- Public Library Association (see NEH) 29
- Rare Books Conference on Facsimiles 35
- Royal College of Art, London 44
- Society of American Archivists 35
- Southwestern Library Association 24
- Stanford University (see NEH) 24
- State University of New York at Stony Brook (see NEH) 15
- Swarthmore College (see NEH) 13
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- University of North Carolina 25
- University of Pennsylvania 35
- Vanderbilt University 15
- Wabash College 15

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent nonprofit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960, in 1967, and again in 1971 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling eighteen million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts much of its work through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

